

FRAMEWORK CONTRACT SMART 2019/0024 LOT 2 - EXPLORING, DOCUMENTING AND ANALYSING DIGITAL POLICY ISSUES

5G SUPPLY MARKET TRENDS

Baseline Scenario Report

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ABBREVIATIONS

Abbreviation	Meaning
3GPP	3rd generation partnership project
5GC	5G core
AAU	Active antenna unit
AMF	Access management function
AR	Augmented reality
ARPU	Average revenue per user
BBU	Baseband unit
BM	Bare metal
BSS	Business support system
BTS	Base station
CAPEX	Capital expenses
C-Band	3.4–3.7 GHz
CEX	Customer experience
CNF	Core network function
COTS	Commercial off-the-shelf
CPU	Central processing unit
C-RAN	Centralized/Cloud RAN: concentrating and consolidating the baseband functionality across a smaller number of sites across the telco's network and cloud.
CU	Centralized unit
CVP	Core value proposition
DC	Data center
D-RAN	Decentralized RAN
DSS	Dynamic spectrum sharing
DU	Distributed unit
E2E	End to end
eCPRI	Enhanced common public radio interface
eMBB	Enhanced mobile broadband
EPC	Evolved packet core
EPS	Evolved packet system
ETSI	Organization for European Standards
FWA	Fixed wireless access
GSMA	Groupe Speciale Mobile Association
HW	Hardware
IoT	Internet of Things
MANO	Management and network orchestration
MEC	Mobile edge computing
MIMO	Multiple-in, Multiple-out
mMTC	massive machine type communication
mmWave	Milimeter Wave
MNO	Mobile Network Operator

NaaS	Network as a Service
NEP	Network Equipment Provider
NFV	Network function virtualization
NFVI	Network function virtualization infrastructure
NR	New radio
NSA	Non-standalone
OPEX	Operational expenses
oRAN	Open RAN: disaggregated RAN functionality built using open interface specifications between elements. Can be implemented in vendor-neutral hardware and software-defined technology based on open interfaces and community-developed standards.
O-RAN Alliance	O-RAN Alliance is a specification group defining next generation RAN infrastructures, adhering to the principles of intelligence and openness.
OSS	Operations support system
QoS	Quality of service
RAN	Radio Access Network
RFP	Requests for proposals
RRH	Remote radio head
SA	Standalone
SDN	Software defined networking
SMF	Session management function
TCO	Total cost of ownership
TIP	Telecom infra project
UL	Uplink
UP	User plane
URLLC	Ultra reliable low latency communication
vBBU	Virtual baseband unit
vCU	Virtual centralized unit
vDU	Virtual distributed unit
vEPC	Virtual evolved packet core
VM	Virtual machine
VNF	Virtual network function
VoNR	Voice over new radio
VR	Virtual reality
vRAN	Virtual RAN: an implementation of the RAN in a more open and flexible architecture which virtualizes network functions in software platforms based on general purpose processors.

1 INTRODUCTION

The objective of the Baseline Scenario Report (D3) is to present the current 4G and 5G supply chain and market shares of infrastructure providers in the most relevant regions and the largest EU markets. The scope of this report is to create a general overview of the most prominent players in the 4G and 5G network equipment space (Subtask 1.1) and to create an overview on the geographical markets (Subtask 1.2). For the compilation of this report, qualitative and quantitative data published before end of October 2020 has been taken into account.

1.1 Research methodology

To derive this report, a combination of secondary- and primary market research was used. By leveraging secondary sources, an initial generic overview of the most prominent players in the 4G and 5G network equipment space has been created. Secondary research sources included Arthur D. Little’s proprietary database, annual reports, company websites, press releases, investor presentations of selected companies, white papers, certified publications, directories and external databases. The most notable external databases referred to include Allied Market Research, Dell’Oro, Gartner, Grand View Research, MarketsandMarkets, GM Insights, and Market Research Future. A diagram of notable sources is given in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Research methodology

Alongside secondary research, extensive data has been obtained through interviews with industry experts, including most of the CTOs of the major mobile network operators (MNOs). In total, over 30 interviews were conducted. The perspectives of some of the most important telecom infrastructure companies were also gathered. Figure 2 below gives an overview of the composition of the multiple industry experts.

Figure 2: Share of ADL industry experts by region and position

Based on total revenue generated in 2019, market-size estimates were created for the EU-27, the UK, the US, China, Japan and South Korea. The analysis looks at public networks, which account for the vast majority of

the market in comparison to private networks, and does not include any of the maintenance, consulting and installation costs associated with deploying and running a network.

2 DEFINING THE 4G AND 5G NETWORK EQUIPMENT SPACE

5G is a new generation of wireless technology that has the potential to completely transform the technological landscape of our world. It follows previous generations of mobile technology like 3G, which led to the launch of smartphones, and 4G, which enabled faster browsing and video streaming. In the case of 5G, the high bandwidth and low latency provided enables an entire swathe of new technologies, such as IOT devices, autonomous vehicles, and VR.

Yet the advent of 5G is not a single event. Instead 5G is a path, and there are two possible methods to manage the transition from 4G/LTE to 5G: standalone (SA) and non-standalone (NSA). Non-standalone refers to 5G networks that will be built upon, and supported by, existing 4G / LTE infrastructure. In these networks, legacy 4G Evolved Packet Core (EPC) technology is maintained in the core. Meanwhile, standalone 5G networks will be built from scratch, using 5G new radio and 5G core (5GC) to unlock the full potential of 5G, and offer superior speed and latency. Figure 3 offers a basic graphic of SA and NSA networks.

Figure 3: 5G non-standalone vs. 5G standalone networks

Established MNOs initially tend to take a path towards DSS and non-standalone solutions as they continue to make use of pre-existing legacy 4G infrastructure, and thus less initial CAPEX is required since not every 4G component must be replaced. Of course, over time, the 4G legacy equipment will be phased out and replaced with new 5G equipment. However, the longer timeframe of this CAPEX means less money is required upfront and the investment can be spread out to reduce its cost. On the other hand, green-field operators typically favor the standalone approach since they do not have legacy infrastructure in place and can directly opt for a network based entirely on 5G components.

As the transition from 4G to 5G is a smooth transition rather than a clear-cut one, in this report the 4G and 5G network equipment space will be analyzed across both non-standalone and standalone networks. Furthermore, in order to cover the whole 5G topic, in addition to the *Radio Access Network* (RAN) and *Core* domain, the focus will lie on two other network domains (four in total): *Transport & Data Center* (DC) and *Systems*, i.e. *Operations Support Systems* (OSS). All four network domains will be illustrated in depth in the body of the report.

The views and opinions expressed in this paper are primarily the result of extensive interviews of the leading CTOs of leading MNOs – over 30 experts were interviewed, the majority of which are from Europe and the US. A full breakdown of expert demographics, as well as a broader explanation of the methodology for the paper's data, are given in the body of the paper.

3 OVERVIEW OF GLOBAL 5G ROLLOUTS

The 5G era has begun. Rollouts have started across the world and are beginning to reach the point of scale at which 5G can be sold as a reliable product to consumers and businesses. Operators in South Korea, China, and North America are most advanced globally in their 5G rollouts and have begun offering their services to customers on a broader basis. In Europe, however, 5G remains a goal more than a reality.

3.1 Europe's rollouts vary drastically in progress

5G coverage in Europe is very limited so far, with a small number of base stations compared those of front runners such as South Korea, Japan, and China. The more advanced countries include Germany, Switzerland, the Netherlands, and Finland.

Currently rollouts are all NSA, with plans to switch to SA during 2021/22; most Cores are already fully virtualized, though not yet running containers on bare metal. DSS has been consistently used to increase population coverage without investments in building out platforms, which prompted criticism from some experts, who claim that DSS isn't real 5G, but only offers similar speeds to 4G. Market experts even state that DSS will "ruin the customer perception of 5G."

German rollouts are some of the most advanced in Europe, but still only consist of installing at most a few thousand base stations in 2020: Deutsche Telekom expects to deploy 1,500 5G new radio base stations across Germany by the end of 2020, and continue to build 2,000 new sites every year.¹ By using DSS, Deutsche Telekom announced 50 percent 5G population coverage in July 2020 and targets a two-thirds population coverage by the end of the year, with a boost from the first iPhone rollout.² Telefonica has also embraced DSS and plans for one-third population coverage by the end of 2020. Despite COVID-19, MNOs have invested as predicted; Deutsche Telekom will invest EUR 20 bn (approximately 25 percent of its 2019 annual revenues) in Germany by 2021, and Telefonica has accelerated investments, increasing CAPEX from 12 percent of revenues to 18–19 percent.³

In Italy, rollouts began in 2019, with Vodafone announcing its first launch in five of the largest Italian cities. Wind Tre followed, launching 5G in mid-2020 and, since then, achieving 40 percent population coverage as of October 2020 via DSS. The operator expects national coverage by early 2021. Telecom Italia is deploying at a similar pace. However, neither Telecom Italia nor Vodafone has the prerequisite base stations to use DSS.

In Switzerland, MNO Swisscom achieved 90 percent population coverage by the end of 2019, and fellow Swiss MNO Sunrise had already achieved 80 percent as of August 2019.⁴ Indeed, Sunrise claimed that its 5G rollout had been one of the most aggressive in the company's history. Demographics play some role: population is mostly concentrated in a few dense urban localized areas in Switzerland, while much of the rest of the country is sparsely inhabited. This means even a small number of installations can cover a remarkably large percentage of the population. High disposable incomes, which facilitate the possibility of consumer spend on 5G, also play a part in Swiss 5G leadership

Elsewhere in Europe, however, rollouts are less advanced. As of September 2020, more than half of the European Union's 27 member countries had not yet launched 5G commercial services.⁵ Most obviously absent is France, which, as of October 2020, had still not launched any 5G services. This is hardly surprising, given the government had only hosted its spectrum auction in September 2020 and MNOs so far had not time to organize full-scale rollouts.

In some sense, Europe suffers in 5G because of its strength in 4G. 4G networks are well built and maintained and provide extensive coverage across the continent. For example, in Norway, huge investments were made in 4G deployments, and even in the most northern and sparsely populated areas of the country, 4G is

¹ <https://www.rcrwireless.com/20191206/5g/deutsche-telekom-end-2019-450-sites-suspends-5g-deals>

² <https://techblog.comsoc.org/2020/07/27/deutsche-telekom-40-million-people-have-5g-coverage/#:~:text=Deutsche%20Telekom%20said%20today%20that,the%20new%205G%20mobile%20technology.&text=The%20company%20uses%20both%20the,bands%20for%20the%205G%20rollout.>

³ <https://www.telecomlead.com/5g/deutsche-telekom-reveals-eight-point-5g-investment-strategy-86826>

⁴ <https://lenews.ch/2019/12/27/swisscom-achieves-90-percent-5g-coverage-despite-resistance/#:~:text=Swisscom%2C%20Switzerland's%20largest%20mobile%20operator,by%20the%20end%20of%202019.&text=Switzerland%20is%20a%20world%20leader,%2C%20according%20to%20speedtest.net.>

⁵ <https://www.wsj.com/articles/europe-is-falling-behind-on-5g-rollout-top-companies-warn-11600408801>

ubiquitous. The same intensity of investment is unlikely for 5G in the near future. In Switzerland, which already has some of the best 4G networks in Europe and the world, many believe there is no pressing need to invest in 5G. Subsequently, while there is support for 5G at the federal level in Switzerland, in some areas regulation is extremely strict at a local level – “10 times stricter” than the rest of Europe according to a market expert. Though this has rarely been a problem in the densely populated cities (hence why early rollouts have been so fast), it has hampered base-station deployment in many of the rural French areas of the country.⁶

Across industry experts, the same story is heard: MNOs are struggling to find the right business case for 5G. Consumers are indifferent toward higher broadband speeds, and business use cases have not yet been fully explored. Thus, rollouts have primarily remained localized public relations affairs, with operators racing to be the first to rollout in each city. 5G does not have the same rollout speed as LTE, for which huge investments were made even in some of the most rural areas of Europe. Although there is political interest to be at the forefront of 5G rollouts, this hasn't manifested itself in the way European governments have implemented their spectrum auctions, regulation, or government support.

3.2 Huawei bans have delayed UK rollouts

The UK government sees leadership in 5G as a tool to signal that the UK is a forward-thinking, tech-embracing country. With Brexit looming, 5G is a key part of the UK's strategy to define itself outside of the EU. As such, the government has put substantial effort into facilitating a range of 5G incubation events, and all four operators have launched quickly and heavily invested in these events. In the UK, EE installed 1,500 sites in 2019, and Vodafone plans to have installed 1,000 sites by the end of 2020. The first commercial implementations are coming in 2020, along with the release of the iPhone 12. Yet, according to an expert in the UK, it is still “a three-year timeline until we get to a point of anything near scale.”

The lack of a clear government stance over Huawei has also complicated rollouts significantly. Initially refusing to ban Huawei, then moving to a provision that allowed a maximum of 35 percent Huawei in the network, before finally declaring that all Huawei equipment must be gone by 2028, has disrupted operator timelines and scheduled spend. UK culture secretary Oliver Dowden announced that this might result in “a cumulative delay to 5G rollout of two to three years” and cost operators a further GBP 2 bn.⁷

3.3 The US opts for a market-driven rollout

The USA has begun its 5G rollout, and US MNOs, left to their own devices, are ahead of those in Europe. As of April 2020, American carriers had installed 10,000 5G base stations.⁸ Most US mobile network operators have already awarded multi-year contracts for 5G deployment, including two USD 3.5 billion contracts signed by T-Mobile with Ericsson and Nokia.⁹ Verizon and AT&T both launched their first commercial 5G services in April 2019, and continued to expand across cities during the second half of 2019. In October 2020, Verizon deployed DSS nationwide, and demonstrated that it could generate up to 5 gigabit throughput to end-user devices using mmWave spectrum.

Like Europe, the US has struggled to make a consumer use case for 5G – consumers don't see differentiation between 4G and 5G, and both Verizon and T-Mobile have admitted data speeds are similar across the two networks. Devices also need to catch up, though the launch of the new 5G-enabled iPhone in October 2020 will help drive consumer take-up, say experts.

3.4 The 5G ascendency of China and South Korea

China and South Korea are by far the world's two leading 5G countries by almost any metric. Chinese operators built a total of 257,000 new 5G base stations in the first half of 2020, to bring the total number of 5G base stations to 410,000 as of June.¹⁰ Another 600,000 5G base stations are scheduled to be deployed by the end of the year. Meanwhile, in South Korea, during the first half of 2019, LG Uplus installed 50,000 5G base

⁶ <https://www.rcrwireless.com/20200504/5g/regulations-challenge-swisscom-5g-deployments-some-regions#:~:text=Switzerland's%20Federal%20Council%20recently%20decided,radiation%20by%20maintaining%20its%20limits.>

⁷ <https://www.theguardian.com/technology/2020/jul/14/huawei-decision-may-delay-5g-rollout-by-three-years-and-cost-uk-7bn->

⁸ <https://www.economist.com/business/2020/04/08/america-does-not-want-china-to-dominate-5g-mobile-networks>

⁹ [https://www.lightreading.com/mobile/5g/ericsson-lands-\\$35b-5g-deal-with-t-mobile-weeks-after-nokia-did-same/d/d-id/745992](https://www.lightreading.com/mobile/5g/ericsson-lands-$35b-5g-deal-with-t-mobile-weeks-after-nokia-did-same/d/d-id/745992)

¹⁰ <https://www.rcrwireless.com/20200728/5g/chinese-telcos-deploy-257000-5g-base-stations-h1-2020-report>

stations, Korea Telecom installed another 30,000, and SK Telecom deployed 54,000.¹¹ These figures dwarf European installation figures.

All three South Korean operators launched their services on the same day in April 2019 and the country surpassed the 3 mn 5G subscriber mark on September 9, 2019. China launched in late 2019 – Yang Chaobin, president of Huawei’s wireless network product line, predicts that by the end of 2020, China’s network will provide services to over 200 mn users, well over 70 percent of the world’s 5G users.¹² Figure 4: 5G subscribers (in thousands) across geographic regions depicts IDATE DigiWorld’s projection of 5G subscriber shares until 2025, from which it is clear to see China’s dominant position.

Figure 4: 5G subscribers (in thousands) across geographic regions¹³

According to Groupe Speciale Mobile Association (GSMA), the first stage of 5G investments corresponds to early deployments between 2018 and 2020, with USD 140 bn spent in the US, South Korea, Japan, and China. The five largest European countries will contribute USD 30 bn and Gulf Corporation Council (GCC) players will spend roughly USD 5 bn. Over the next five years, APAC will spend almost USD 400 bn, and Europe will spend roughly USD 200 bn. This discrepancy in CAPEX is further outlined in Figure 5.

Figure 5: Non-5G CAPEX and 5G CAPEX across regions, USD bn, cumulative from 2018-25¹⁴

¹¹ <http://5gobservatory.eu/wp-content/uploads/2019/07/80082-5G-Observatory-Quarterly-report-4-min.pdf>

¹² <https://syncedreview.com/2020/08/06/huawei-china-to-have-800k-5g-base-stations-by-end-of-2020/>

¹³ <https://fr.idate.org/produit/5g-markets-in-europe-dataset-report/>

¹⁴ GSMA Intelligence

COVID-19 is not thought to have had a significant impact on these CAPEX figures. Although the pandemic delayed some 2020 investment into 2021, most experts believe investment will proceed as planned during the next half-decade.

4 5G TRENDS IN EUROPE

4.1 Expensive European spectrum auctions

In certain areas of Europe, high spectrum prices have raised eyebrows. Italian 5G rollouts began with a spectrum auction that raised an eye-watering EUR 6.55 bn, EUR 4.35 bn of which came from the auction of 200 MHz of 3.7 GHz airwaves. The intense competition meant that bidders in the Italian 3.7 GHz sale paid around \$0.42 per MHz per head of population (per MHz pop), which is well above what was raised in other countries. The UK's auction saw a price of \$0.17 per MHz pop, while in Spain and Ireland the price paid was well below \$0.10 per MHz pop. In Finland, one of the most advanced European 5G countries, the price was around one-tenth of what was fetched in Italy. German auctions were also priced highly, with operators paying \$0.20 per MHz pop.

Other countries have not yet even auctioned spectrum: Sweden has organized its 3.5 GHz auction for November 2020, and Denmark has postponed its own to March 2021; France was the last of the major European countries to complete auctions, finishing in September 2020. Just 25.5 percent of 5G spectrum had been released in Europe as of September 2020. By contrast, Switzerland, one of the leading countries in Europe, was also one of the earliest, organizing its auctions in January 2019, which exhibits the importance of planning spectrum auctions early to allow MNOs time to plan their rollouts.

4.2 European MNOs are struggling

One important factor explaining the delay in European rollouts is the difficult situation of MNOs in Europe, with limited growth and revenues. As far as revenues from mobile services are concerned, mobile average revenue per user (ARPU) has been declining or remained flat in all regions (-14.4 percent globally between 2012 and 2017), and is much lower in Europe than in North America (see Figure 6) as a result of high levels of competition and a lack of consolidation in the market. While clearly a good thing for consumers, it leaves mobile operators with less cash for 5G investments. Thus, the cost relative to revenues, and subsequent risk of the investment, is significantly higher for EU players.

Figure 6: Mobile ARPU by region, EUR/month¹⁵

Even within Europe, there is a clear link between ARPU and speed of 5G deployments – Switzerland, one of the furthest on the road to 5G deployment, also has one of the highest ARPUs in the world.¹⁶

The broader trend of decreasing MNO profit margins in Europe, together with expensive auctions, often does not leave MNOs enough money to invest in 5G. According to one expert, “the long-term health and survival of MNOs is threatened, as seven out of 10 MNOs do not cover their cost of capital anymore. This leads to less investments in 5G, as MNOs simply lack the cash to pursue them.” Regulators have successfully pushed for

¹⁵ IDATE DigiWorld, State of Telecom Services & Players Worldwide, December 2018

¹⁶ <https://www.zdnet.com/article/a-new-dawn-after-sunrise-how-will-switzerlands-mobile-transformation-play-out/>

competition over the last decade, which has driven down prices for consumers, but left MNOs with less money to invest.

Interestingly, as Figure 6 shows, although ARPU may be significantly lower in Europe than in North America, it is lower still in APAC, and yet countries in APAC (namely China, South Korea and Japan) are leading the 5G charge. However, despite lower ARPU in APAC, operating costs are also lower, which offsets some of the difference in revenue. Perhaps more importantly, leading APAC countries have received some support for rollouts through government initiatives. This support has not been as forthcoming in Europe.

4.3 Europe lacks cohesion and scale in public initiatives

Many European countries have also launched national 5G research & development programs, though the scale of the programs varies drastically from country to country. The UK government has invested substantially, offering EUR 834 million to 5G trials and full fiber deployment across the UK by 2020/21. German institutions have invested EUR 100 million from the “Gigabit Germany Initiative for the Future” and a further EUR 80 million from the “5G Initiative for Germany”. Finland financed research, development and innovation with EUR 467 million of funding (including EUR 6 million from EU structural funds) for 3,760 projects in 2016. Given the relative size and low-density population of Finland, this is a substantial investment by any means.

However, much of the rest of Europe has lagged behind in terms of national development programs. Existing programmes have tended to be small scale and focused on research and testing, rather than provision of funding for broader implementation.

Furthermore, government investments in Europe have tended to be on a national level, and there has been little guidance or direction from the European Union. On a European level, initiatives include the European 5G Infrastructure Public Private Partnership (5G-PPP), which represents a EUR 3.5 billion investment in 5G with EUR 700 million of public investment. Public funding for Phase 1 (2014-2016) was EUR 128 million, Phase 2 represented EUR 149 million, and Phase 3 accounted for the remaining budget of EUR 423 million.

In Horizon 2020 six projects on beyond 5G have been granted by European Commission in the volume of EUR 18 million in the 2016 call (Topic Code ICT-09-2017), 8 projects on the 5G long term evolution in the 2019 call (ICT-20-2019-2020) in the volume of EUR 46 million, and 9 projects on the topic beyond 5G (ICT-52-2020) in the volume of EUR 60 million.¹⁷ As a contrast, EU investments from 2007 to 2013 in research on future networks (half of which was allocated to wireless technologies that contributed to the development of 4G) amounted to roughly EUR 600 million.¹⁸

These investments pale in comparison to those in APAC. China’s government initiatives plan to invest over USD 150 billion by 2025 in 5G networks, which will dwarf any other countries’ investments.¹⁹ In South Korea, the Korean government and 5G Forum, a public-private partnership, defined the 5G mobile strategy as early as January 2014, and allocated USD 1.5 billion, a huge figure for a country with a population of roughly 50mn as of 2020. Furthermore, spurred on by Samsung (which has significant influence on government policy), the Korean government contributed significant support to 5G through tax breaks and subsidies for MNOs that invest in their 5G infrastructure networks.

4.4 Leading 5G countries embrace both supply and demand

The slow pace of deployment of new infrastructure in Europe is a result of a lack of investment from both MNOs and governmental institutions. This is exacerbated by the lack of sufficient synergies between national and European initiatives supporting 5G, as well as of coordination among spectrum policies. Europe is not lagging significantly behind the US, China, South Korea and Japan from a technological standpoint, and possesses key strategic strengths, such as leading equipment manufacturers Ericsson and Nokia and the key 5G standards organization, ETSI/3GPP. However, common European initiatives in fostering the development of 5G infrastructure are missing. Not only does this lead to significant differences in development speed among countries (e.g., Germany versus France), but it also enlarges the gap between Europe and the rest of the world.

¹⁷ In 2016 Topic Code ICT-09-2017, in 2019/2020 Topic Codes ICT-20-2019-2020 and ICT-52-2020.

¹⁸ <https://ec.europa.eu/digital-single-market/en/news/5g-public-private-partnership-next-generation-broadband-infrastructure>

¹⁹ <https://www.rcrwireless.com/20190702/5g/china-invest-over-150-billion-5g-networks-2025-report>

Moreover, given the current political uncertainty surrounding Huawei, Europe could further support its infrastructure providers. In countries with restrictions on Huawei, new network infrastructure projects are likely to use Ericsson and Nokia equipment because the Huawei and ZTE alternatives are no longer possible. What appears to be lucrative for European infrastructure providers also represents an opportunity for software-based “new kids on the block” vendors to fill this gap – MNOs don’t wish to be entirely dependent on the established players, and “new kids” offer the potential for diversification.

5 CHANGING MARKET REQUIREMENTS

Today’s mobile networks are in a constant race to keep up with growing demand for coverage, capacity and customer experience (CEX). The aim of 5G is to deliver internet access at broadband speeds in the order of 10 Gbps, about 100 times faster than theoretically possible with the current technology, LTE. Business drivers behind this advance are the need to:

- Transport much larger volumes of data more quickly for video entertainment content and live streaming on social networks
- Reduce response time (latency) across the mobile network for gaming and certain vertical business applications, e.g., IoT applications such as real-time manufacturing and autonomous vehicles

Broadly speaking, these factors support three use cases, each with slightly different needs:

1. **Enhanced or extreme mobile broadband (eMBB)** – which provides high-bandwidth data streams for entertainment, video, and multimedia communications at higher resolution
2. **Massive machine type communication (mMTC)** – designed for wide area coverage of hundreds of thousands of devices in a small radius, typically to ensure reliable connectivity for multiple small units with low-medium bandwidth requirements – e.g., pollution monitoring in a city
3. **Ultra-reliable and low-latency communications (URLLC)** – very low latency and high reliability allows monitoring and control of machines in real time, with use cases in industrial settings, such as controlling automatic guided vehicles (AGVs)

Achieving today’s customer demands for super-high throughput and ultra-low latencies has encouraged rethinking of traditional mobile network architectures in order to provide the flexibility, scalability and degree of automation that is required in the era of 5G. Technology developments in the fields of hardware and software disaggregation and network-function virtualization and containerization will allow for radical architectural changes across mobile network domains. To fully reap the benefits of network virtualization, telco operators have begun to rethink sourcing and deployment models, as well as corresponding organizational set-ups.

5.1 Technological changes

Alongside the shift in industry demand, and in part encouraged by this shift, novel (for the telecom sector, yet not for ICT as a whole) architecture concepts have begun taking hold. These include:

1. **“Softwarization” and virtualization of network functions** – End-to-end software-defined networks (SDNs) allow for the scalability and automation required for future 5G use cases. Virtualization of Basebands (BBUs) increases computing flexibility, which allows it to be more efficiently allocated, thus increasing average equipment utilization and reducing the total amount of equipment necessary to facilitate the network. Virtualization also improves CEX by reducing the risk of congestion.
2. **Disaggregation of hardware (HW) and software (SW)** – Unbundling of HW and SW (i.e., using commercial off-the-shelf compute storage and networking hardware) is nothing new, yet it only recently gained general exposure across networking equipment (especially in RANs). The resulting sourcing diversification that is possible can dramatically reduce CAPEX, since vendors must compete on prices for individual pieces of hardware and software and have less ability to force MNOs to buy infrastructure package deals.
3. **Edge and far-edge data center (DC) infrastructure** – Deployment of virtual network functions (VNFs) close to the customer reduces latency, thus improving quality of experience (QoE); enables higher security (especially for mission-/safety-critical applications); and provides local data termination to relieve backbone network traffic. This is particularly crucial for URLLC use cases.
4. **Containerization of software** – Moving from dedicated servers and virtual machines (VMs) to containers on “bare metal” (i.e., running VNFs on a significantly reduced stack) to further increase efficiency and hardware usage and drive scalability of the network.

5. **Open interfaces** – Standardization of application programming interfaces (APIs) between, as well as within, network domains allows for vendor competition, hence product innovation by infrastructure firms and a lower total cost of ownership (TCO) for the MNO purchasing the equipment.

5.2 Market catalysts

Many of these technological trends have been around for some time. However, we now see three key market trends acting as catalysts for the large-scale adoption of these technologies in the near future:

1. Interoperability of vendors within and between the individual network domains (RAN, transport, core and orchestration) will further develop at a rapid pace, also based on specifications developed by the O-RAN Alliance.
2. As a consequence of this expansion, the vendor landscape is in a process of broadening drastically, which contributes to the availability of competitive solutions for all network domains on the market, thereby fostering a clear paradigm shift of traditional and “new” network equipment providers (NEPs) to move from monolithic telecom network infrastructure to software-based IT solutions.
3. Technology development will soon reach a point when significant expected network TCO savings can be achieved, through establishment of an ecosystem of suitable integration partners, from which the best and cheapest technologies can be chosen in a “pick and mix” style. With TCO savings, integration efforts and risk for decoupled and disaggregated solutions will seem reasonable.

Overall, in the course of the roll-out of 5G cores and radios, RAN is evolving to a more open, virtualised and distributed architecture. In this process, the merits of a more open, multi-vendor architecture (oRAN, vRAN and C-RAN together) are being promoted by vendors such as Mavenir, Parallel Wireless and AltioStar, whereas a more single-vendor proprietary architecture (C-RAN and vRAN, without oRAN) are being promoted by strong incumbent vendors such as Nokia, Ericsson and Huawei.

Leading telco operators across the globe have already taken the first steps toward these target networks, as illustrated in Figure 7.

Figure 7: Global overview of vRAN/oRAN deployments²⁰

Although virtualization concepts and subsequent target network architectures remain at early stages of development, the first live deployments – such as those by Rakuten in Japan, AT&T in the US and Telefonica in selected markets – have begun.

With a broadening vendor landscape, higher interoperability and performance improvements along the customer journey, operators such as Rakuten, China Mobile and T-Mobile US that deploy virtual RAN

²⁰ Publicly available information from operators, ADL analysis update from:

https://www.adlittle.com/sites/default/files/reports/adl_mobile_network_architecture.pdf

(vRAN)/Open RAN (oRAN) solutions realize network TCO savings of up to 44 percent compared to traditional distributed/centralized RAN setups (D-RAN/C-RAN)²¹. (See Figure 8)

Figure 8: Illustrative TCO savings of vRAN/oRAN compared to traditional RAN setups²²

To realize the benefits of virtualization, organizations must revisit mobile network architectures across domains and explore the organizational changes and alterations of traditional sourcing models that are required. This is a backdrop upon which MNOs plan their 5G rollouts and choose their infrastructure vendors. It is also the backdrop upon which the incumbent vendors set their prices – set them too high, and oRAN development will accelerate.

6 OVERVIEW OF THE VENDOR LANDSCAPE

Historically, established telecom players such as Ericsson and Nokia have dominated the market with their integrated product offerings. Telecom infrastructure based on proprietary hardware has been standard. Despite certain standardizations, interfaces have remained closed for many components. Since telecoms infrastructure has been sold as an integrated product, and products from different companies have not always been configured to work together in the same domain, MNOs have traditionally purchased a small number of integrated network solutions. New players have struggled to enter the market, unable to offer complete packages of integrated products and lacking the economies of scale of established players.

Nowadays, the story across the physical network is one of virtualization, which enables distributed systems and the disaggregation of software and hardware. Disaggregation of hardware and software in combination with subsequent network function virtualization allows moving toward greater vendor diversity and ultimately raises the strategic question of whether to buy pre-integrated solutions from traditional network equipment providers or to source highly specialized IT-based solutions from upcoming “new kids on the block”.

New infrastructure players are not important so far, but will likely become more visible over the next five years. Currently the established mobile network providers still lead the pack (Figure 9). Most experts expect oRAN to become technologically reliable at a low TCO from the end of 2024 onwards. The growing presence of “new players” can be seen in the estimates of Figure 10, based on IHS market data – new players almost double in market share, from roughly 4 percent in 2019 to 7 percent in 2025. Since the technology is not yet fully mature, in 2020 new players are predominantly involved in government and MNO pilot schemes. However, as oRAN technology advances, they will begin to play a greater role in large-scale rollouts across the world. Particularly with the current political uncertainty surrounding Huawei, these new vendors will be fundamental to increasing innovation in a market with few players, as well as ensuring that prices remain low through competition.

²¹ ADL analysis based upon publicly available information from operators: Rakuten claims to have 40% savings in OPEX and 30% savings in CAPEX using vRAN, China Mobile 53% opex and 30% CAPEX with savings in power consumption, site rental fees on site management and repairs and T Mobile reports that oRAN can reduce CAPEX for 5G by up to 50% compared with 4G.

²² Publicly available information from operators, ADL analysis.

Global market share for 5G vendors

H1 2020, in % of market value

Figure 9: H1 2020 5G market shares²³

Figure 10: Core and RAN market-share forecasts²⁴

For now, the global 4G and 5G infrastructure market is dominated by four incumbent firms: Ericsson, Huawei, Nokia, and ZTE. These four firms all offer end-to-end solutions and a full swathe of infrastructure components. Samsung, the South Korean technology giant and a more recent entrant to the vendor market, along with the “new kids on the block”, does not yet offer end-to-end solutions across networks (Samsung is close but lacks support for legacy 2G and 3G infrastructure). An illustrative offering of selected vendors is given below in Figure 11.

²³ Global 5G market shares based on Dell’Oro Group market reports for H1 2020

²⁴ DNB Markets illustration based on IHS Market data. NB: percentages do not add up to 100% due to rounding.

Figure 11: Overview of relevant players

The subsequent section is devoted to deep-dives into each of the main vendors, as well as an overview of some of the most promising “new kids on the block”.

6.1 Ericsson

Ericsson is a Swedish vendor with a roughly 28 percent market share worldwide and a strong RAN as well as Core offering.²⁵ Ericsson has a large European presence – among others, Telenor Norway is piloting its 5G network with Ericsson, Vodafone is rolling out its London network, and – as well as a strong global presence overall – among others, Ericsson provides RAN for Verizon and Softbank and is building T-Mobile US’s 5G core. As of February 2020, Ericsson claimed 81 5G agreements, has named 35 5G customers and points out that 25 5G networks are “live.”²⁶ Market experts estimate that the company is involved in 70 out of every 100 5G rollouts globally.²⁷

Alongside Huawei, Ericsson is considered to be one of the most advanced vendors. In some categories Ericsson is the clear market leader such as Dynamic Spectrum Sharing (DSS) – Ericsson’s DSS is helping Deutsche Telekom to hit 50 percent 5G population coverage in Germany by mid-2020, and two-thirds by the end of 2020. In 5G contributions, Ericsson is second only to Huawei, and together the two companies make up 45 percent of all contributions related to 5G technology development. This can be seen in Figure 12.

²⁵ <https://www.telecomlead.com/telecom-statistics/ericsson-closes-the-gap-in-mobile-infrastructure-market-share-with-huawei-82888>

²⁶ <https://www.lightreading.com/5g/ericsson-huawei-and-nokias-5g-wins-are-no-big-deal/a/d-id/757677>

²⁷ Based on Arthur D. Little expert interviews, including 40+ CTOs globally

Figure 12: Number of 5G contributions per NEP, 2015 - 2020²⁸

Ericsson stands to benefit significantly from political uncertainty across the Western world regarding Huawei as it is viewed as perhaps the safest and most reliable vendor choice. In contrast, Nokia is perceived by some to be on the back foot after some early 5G slips, Samsung lacks experience and only has a limited legacy portfolio, and oRAN is not considered to be ready yet. Ericsson is thus the clear choice for any MNO looking to replace Huawei equipment. Indeed, in October 2020, the UK's BT, one of the MNOs hardest hit by the UK's restrictions of Huawei equipment, recently confirmed a 5G deal with Ericsson to replace Huawei in the RAN – in time it's expected that 50% of traffic will flow through Ericsson's kit.²⁹

In the past, Ericsson has not been too active in the oRAN space, claiming that general-purpose processors could not match the performance of its own customized gear and that there remained unresolved security concerns around a disaggregated vendor setup. Although some of these problems remain, Ericsson is now a leading member of the O-RAN Alliance, and in June 2020, acknowledged the future potential of oRAN when it told investors it needed to be the first player to provide oRAN-compliant products once the technology had improved.

6.2 Nokia

Nokia is a Finnish vendor with a long history of experience in telecoms infrastructure, IT and consumer electronics. Nokia is perceived by some experts to have fallen behind other leading vendors in recent years in terms of technological performance, as can be seen by the number of Nokia's submitted contributions in Figure 10, but still has a strong global presence. Multiple experts believe Nokia also maintains key strengths around tech and services in packet core as well as a broader product portfolio than Nordic rival Ericsson. As of February 2020, Nokia claimed 67 5G deals, 40 named 5G customers and 19 "live" 5G networks.³⁰

However, Verizon's recent contract with Samsung has fuelled speculation that Verizon means to replace Nokia in parts of its network, which reflects some of the challenges Nokia was perceived to have been facing with its 5G technology. The markets where Nokia was supplying 5G gear in the US for Sprint– Los Angeles, New York City, Phoenix and Washington, D.C. – were all behind schedule in launching their 5G networks due to a delay in the availability of Nokia software in the RAN.

Nokia has reacted to uncertain times by looking into top-line (revenue) and bottom-line (cost) measures. As part of these measures, in 2019, Nokia's headcount decreased by roughly 5 percent, and in June 2020, the company revealed it would cut 1,233 jobs in France, affecting R&D at two French facilities. News of R&D cuts is a potential concern given that Nokia is already the only one of the "big five" vendors whose R&D investments have markedly declined in the last couple of years – see Figure 11.

²⁸ https://omdia.tech.informa.com/-/media/tech/omdia/brochures/service-providers/omdia_3gpp_2020_contribution_whitepaper.pdf

²⁹ <https://www.bbc.co.uk/news/technology-54716940>

³⁰ <https://www.lightreading.com/5g/ericsson-huawei-and-nokias-5g-wins-are-no-big-deal/a/d-id/757677>

Figure 13: R&D spend across 'big five vendors'³¹

However, with new CEO Pekka Lundmark at the helm, Nokia looks ready to make the necessary changes to re-cement its position at the forefront of the market. "I want to empower my own team at Nokia to challenge and change how we do things if that means we can do things better," Lundmark explained.³²

Furthermore, Nokia sees opportunities in the developments around oRAN, and was the first major vendor to unveil oRAN-compliant goods on June 23, 2020, announcing products that covered every part of the RAN, from radio units and gateways to servers and basebands. General availability, it said, would come the following year. This appears to be a promising path into the future for Nokia.

6.3 Huawei

Huawei is another technology leader within the vendor landscape, offering high quality equipment and service. Huawei has achieved the highest global market share of any vendor, a large increase from its roughly 10 percent market share a decade ago. Contrary to popular belief, Huawei is not always the low-cost player. Instead, Huawei is believed to offer top-tier functionality and service to MNOs, and is one of the most technologically advanced vendors in many categories, as can be seen in the contributions and R&D numbers from Figures Figure 12 and Figure 13. Having already managed 5G deployments at a large scale in China, Huawei has extensive technical expertise in deployment.

Of course, given the recent political uncertainty regarding Huawei, its growth has slowed. Regardless of the underlying reasons for this uncertainty, its effect on the vendor landscape is dramatic. Without Huawei, vendor diversity and competition will decrease – many MNOs have already expressed their disappointment. European MNOs are particularly disappointed because they invested heavily in Huawei's 4G "single RAN" products, which were developed to run 2G, 3G and 4G services over the same platform. The costs of switching these legacy services to other providers will be immense. Thus, most European operators plan to continue using existing Huawei equipment for its full usage cycle if possible, assuming political factors don't necessitate upgrades any sooner.

Huawei has maintained a position of scepticism towards oRAN. Peter Zhou, CMO of Huawei's wireless product line, said in February 2019 that the company's own research had revealed a huge performance gap between white boxes and traditional radio gear. According to this research, using "white boxes with Intel CPUs in 4G base stations" leads to "ten times" higher power consumption.³³ As of October 2020, it is the only one of the "big three" vendors not to have joined the O-RAN Alliance.

³¹ Company reports: <https://www.lightreading.com/5g/nokia-confirms-plan-to-slash-1233-jobs-in-france/d/d-id/761863>. NB: figures not specific to only networks business

³² <https://www.sdxcentral.com/articles/news/nokias-new-ceo-confronts-complacency/2020/08/>

³³ <https://www.lightreading.com/white-box/white-box-systems/white-box-doubts-keep-huawei-on-outside-of-o-ran-alliance/d/d-id/749565>

6.4 Samsung

Samsung is a new entrant to the vendor market with significant financial might and backing from the Korean government. Early projects were based in Samsung's homeland of South Korea, where Samsung helped to facilitate the local 5G rollouts: in 2017 Samsung and SK Telecom announced the successful completion of the world's first 4G LTE and 5G end-to-end network-interworking trial in a real outdoor environment in Seoul. Samsung and KDDI also completed a 5G demonstration on a moving train traveling at over 100 km/hour (over 60 mph).

Although challenges were faced in some of Samsung's earliest rollouts, recent expansion across Asia and America has increased Samsung's market share. The long-running absence of Chinese suppliers in the US brings opportunities: Samsung was recently awarded a USD 6.6 bn contract with Verizon, largely at the expense of Nokia. The deal cements Samsung's position as a major player in the US market.

However, Samsung lacks a broad portfolio of 2G and 3G legacy systems, and thus might not meet the unique technical requirements of many European MNOs. During the 4G era, many European carriers purchased single RAN products, which allowed them to run 2G, 3G, and 4G services over the same platforms, minimizing costs and solving site-related considerations. Samsung does not yet have the capabilities to also support these services, and for that reason, vendors including the UK's BT have decided against Samsung as a Huawei substitute. As such, it is unclear whether Samsung will be able to meaningfully compete in Europe in the near term.

6.5 ZTE

ZTE has grown rapidly over the last decade and has now achieved a roughly 10 percent market share worldwide. ZTE's technical contributions to 5G have been slightly fewer than those of competitors (see Figure 12), but its 5G portfolio has been boosted by the early rollouts in its native China and the company has substantial experience within the context of 5G rollouts.

ZTE is often the vendor of choice in developing countries throughout Africa, the Middle East, South Asia, and in some countries in Europe such as Austria and Italy, as its gear is some of the most cost efficient on the market while maintaining a high standard of performance.

6.6 New kids on the block

The "new kids on the block" represent small companies that are disrupting the traditional vendor market through innovative products or sets of products. Typically, these are software-based products, designed to run on COTS hardware. Altiostar, Mavenir, Parallel Wireless and Affirmed are four of the largest.

Altiostar provides a 4G and 5G open virtualized RAN (Open vRAN) software solution that supports open interfaces to build multi-vendor, web-scale, cloud-based networks. Altiostar closed a USD 114 million Series C round of financing in May 2019, with Rakuten coming on board as an investor alongside Qualcomm and Tech Mahindra. Altiostar shows little presence in Europe but is strong throughout Asia and North America.

Mavenir is the only "new kid on the block" to offer a cloud-native software solution for 4G and 5G across both RAN and Core. Mavenir has a strong presence in Europe, working with Vodafone, Telefonica, and Deutsche Telekom, among others. In August 2020, Vodafone announced that it was the first mobile operator to have turned on a live oRAN 4G site in the U.K., with help of Mavenir. The architecture was based on RRUs and DUs located at the cell site and a CU more than 180 miles away.³⁴ Although impressive, Mavenir is a small company, and competing over the entire stack means it is currently spread rather thin.

Parallel Wireless delivers software-defined, end-to-end 5G, 4G, 3G, and 2G Open RAN solutions – the only "new kid" to specifically cater to legacy systems before 4G. Vodafone has 25 planned trial sites in Turkey carrying commercial traffic over a Parallel Wireless 2G+4G macro site; Telefonica is deploying sites in Peru, Colombia and Argentina for their pilot oRAN trials, using Parallel Wireless and Altiostar; Singtel is performing trials with Parallel Wireless alongside trials with Mavenir.

Affirmed Networks offers a virtualized evolved packet core (vEPC) that lets communication service providers scale with the demands of mobile services. The start-up also offers a fully cloud-native platform for 5G and a

³⁴ <https://www.fiercewireless.com/operators/mavenir-helps-vodafone-turn-uk-s-first-live-4g-openran-site>

range of capabilities in automation and orchestration. Affirmed has raised \$155 million to date. Vodafone UK used Affirmed as part of its IoT platform, with a mixture of good and bad experiences; Affirmed has been present in the Finnish rollouts, used by Finnish operator DNA; and AT&T will be using Affirmed vEPC as part of its Domain 2.0 network. Affirmed, according to one expert, is “particularly interesting from an architectural point of view.”

Microsoft’s acquisitions of Affirmed and Metaswitch represents a foray into telecoms. These moves show tech companies’ growing focus on leveraging cloud architectures and the adoption of 5G to capitalize on a bigger role by becoming service providers to both carriers and those that would like to build carrier-like services (potentially bypassing operators in the process). Microsoft announced its intentions in March 2020 to help operators “manage their network workloads in the cloud... We believe that with innovation in software and by making use of broadly available cloud computing platforms like Microsoft Azure, operators can deploy and maintain 5G networks and services more efficiently, more cost effectively, more rapidly, and more securely.”³⁵

6.7 Timeline for oRAN

New vendors, and their technology, are still at proof-of-concept phase and not yet a threat to the established vendors. According to most experts, oRAN will not be ready, from a performance perspective, to be implemented at scale in existing networks for at least three more years. As of 2020, new vendors are more challenged than they claim in their RFPs – they compete on cost, and often vastly underestimate the volume of equipment an MNO will have to purchase from them to achieve the same capabilities as a traditional system. Yet, “new kids” have already had first success with greenfield deployments such as Rakuten in Japan or Dish in the US due to the lack of legacy technology and hence lower technical complexity.

Until the technology matures, “new kids on the block” have been relegated to the domain of incubation tests and very localized rollouts. Every major MNO is testing the equipment of “new kids” – including Deutsche Telekom, Vodafone, Verizon, Telefonica, Singtel and AT&T – but none have implemented any rollouts with these new vendors. This offers time for traditional vendors to respond: either embrace the new technology or prepare to fight it. Respectively, concerns around security in a disaggregated network are already being raised.

Another concern for “new kids” is finding a way to appeal to smaller MNOs, which do not have the required technical expertise in-house to integrate all the components needed for a network using parts from different vendors, all with slightly different specifications.

However, among experts there is little doubt of the direction in which the market is moving, albeit slowly. Deutsche Telekom Germany is seeking to deploy oRAN for an entire city by the end of 2021. Given the potential for restrictions on Huawei, diversification is paramount for European and American operators, which will do all they can to hurry the development of “new kids”. New kids are already well supported by American operators, who not only want diversification, but also to support American firms in establishing a presence in the cellular networking infrastructure market.

In fact, almost all of the “new kids” are US companies. There are few European “new kids”. This, combined with the US’s intent to establish a presence in the market, is a concern for a Europe that wishes to remain at the forefront of the telecoms landscape. It is also of concern that any new US players will not behave noticeably differently to Chinese vendors from a cyber security perspective. Thus, if US players manage to establish a strong position in the market, this may be dismal for European vendors, while not improving cyber security risks.

6.8 Decline of European vendor landscape

Europe has historically been a leader in telecoms infrastructure vendors, and has fathered large vendors such as Ericsson, Nokia, and Alcatel-Lucent (which began in France as Alcatel).³⁶ Since then, Alcatel-Lucent has disappeared through a merger with Nokia, and both Ericsson and Nokia have lost market share to new Asian vendors, exhibiting Europe’s slowly declining dominance in infrastructure. Furthermore, most of the early innovation in oRAN, virtualization and SDNs did not come from Europe, and Europe cannot claim to have fathered any of the largest “new kids on the block”.

³⁵ <https://blogs.microsoft.com/blog/2020/03/26/microsoft-announces-agreement-to-acquire-affirmed-networks-to-deliver-new-opportunities-for-a-global-5g-ecosystem/>

³⁶ NB: Alcatel merged with American company Lucent in 2006 to form Alcatel Lucent

Concern over this decline of European vendors is widespread across experts – one European expert mentioned that he was “praying for new European vendors”. Europe was at the forefront of telecommunications in the 1990s, with initiatives such as the GSM, which described the protocols for 2G digital cellular networks, and became the global standard for mobile communications by the mid-2010s, achieving over 90 percent market share. There is agreement among experts that if it wants to keep up, Europe needs to be more forward thinking in terms of fostering an environment that supports and promotes technology and digitalization, while championing its infrastructure providers. The challenge for European policy will be in trying to support the vendors while maintaining low prices for MNOs, in order to enable fast 5G rollouts and promote digitization across Europe. But it may even go further: Chinese vendors benefit greatly from a very supportive policy in regard to demand stimulation. Beyond that, both Chinese and US policy is actively pursuing efforts to support the development of applications that require 5G and that, in turn, advance the application capability.

The imminent decline of the European vendor landscape, despite having highly qualified radio technology is not the only concern. Without a strong European network vendor landscape, stimulation of demand-side measures will become harder to justify and thus, any future innovation, be it in the traffic-, the robotics-, the healthcare or any other space, will also be more challenging.

7 ASSESSING THE GLOBAL 4G AND 5G INFRASTRUCTURE MARKET

7.1 Market size and segmentation approach

As a result of extensive analyses, we estimate the global 4G and 5G infrastructure market to be USD 56 bn, 70 percent of which is found in the target geographies of the study. Of this, roughly 35 percent is found in the services, maintenance, installation costs, set-up fees and COTS hardware associated with establishing and operating a mobile network, none of which are within the scope of our study. The remaining 65 percent is the USD 25.4 bn that has been calculated.

Figure 14 offers a graphical representation of the structure of the market breakdown and associated market figures.

Figure 14: Global 4G / 5G market across network domains³⁷

Within Figure 14 are also the headline revenue figures for each network segment. The exact segment definitions are given as follows:

³⁷ Arthur D. Little analysis, expert interviews

7.1.1 RAN – 4G LTE and 5G antenna (AAU/RRH/small cells)

This segment considers the total revenue generated through the sales of active antenna units (AAUs), remote radio heads (RRHs), and small cell antennas (including picocells, femtocells, and microcells) deployed at the base stations to provide 4G LTE and 5G connectivity – for instance, Huawei's LampSite, AtomCell, Pico, and AAUs, among others. However, the consulting, installation and integration, and support and maintenance services associated with deploying these hardware products has not been included in this market sizing.

7.1.2 RAN – 4G basebands

This segment includes the total revenue generated through the sales of all BBU hardware products that provide connectivity to radio antennas in the evolved Node B (eNodeB) 4G LTE architecture. In addition, we have considered the BBUs for eNodeB deployed for both the traditional and centralized RAN architecture. However, the consulting, installation and integration, and support and maintenance services associated with the deployment of these hardware products has not been included within the market sizing, and neither have the software products used to deploy or operate virtualized or centralized RAN network infrastructure. For instance, Samsung's CDU (cabinet type DU), RDU (ruggedized DU), and OCDU (outdoor cabinet type DU) deployed for LTE infrastructure have been considered.

7.1.3 RAN - 5G basebands (CU/DU)

This segment includes the total revenue generated through the sales of BBU hardware and software products that provide connectivity to the 5G new radio (eNodeB) antennas through establishing connectivity with the fronthaul network. Additionally, this segment considers 5G NR BBUs installed for both the centralized unit (CU) and distributed units (DUs) network equipment. However, it does not include the software products used to deploy or operate virtualized or centralized RAN network infrastructure under the segment. (This is in the Net OS & Kubernetes section). Additionally, the consulting, installation and integration, and support and maintenance services associated with these hardware products have also not been considered part of this segment's scope. For instance, Nokia's AirScale baseband modules have been considered.

7.1.4 Core - Evolved packet core (EPC)

This segment considers the total revenue generated through the sales of equipment such as mobility management entity (MME), packet data network gateway (P-GW), serving gateway (S-GW), policy and charging rules function (PCRF), home subscriber server (HSS), and other network and storage elements. However, the software products associated with the virtualized core network infrastructure deployment have not been considered in this segment. Additionally, the revenue generated through services related to the installation and integration of these EPC network infrastructures has not been included. Both on-premise and cloud-based network architectures have been considered. For instance, included is Ericsson's Evolved Packet Gateway equipment, MME, new Converged Packet Gateway (CPG), HSS, and other EPC network elements, as well as Cisco's Ultra Packet Core equipment, which consists of Packet Data Network Gateway (PGW), Mobility Management Entity (MME), Serving Gateway (SGW), Evolved Packet Data Gateway (ePDG), and others.

7.1.5 Core – 5G core

This segment considers the total revenue generated through the sales of 5G core equipment for both the NSA and SA network architecture, which consists of access and mobility management function (AMF), session management function (SMF), user plane function (UPF), policy control function (PCF), authentication server function (AUSF), network exposure function (NEF), NF repository function (NRF), and network slice selection function (NSSF), among others. This includes servers and other network and storage elements required to build cloud-based or virtualized 5G core network architecture. Similarly, the software products deployed for the virtualized or cloud-based 5G core network architecture have not been considered in this segment. Additionally, the revenue generated through installation, integration, and other EPC network infrastructure services has not been included. For instance, Ericsson's set of 5G core network elements under portfolios such as Packet Core Gateway, Enterprise Core, Massive IoT Packet Core, and others, have been included.

7.1.6 Net OS/Kubernetes

This segment considers the total revenue generated through the sales of software (operating system)/Kubernetes – open-source software stack) products (subscriptions or direct purchase) deployed for virtualized or cloud-native RAN and core network. However, the hardware/data center equipment and services parts have not been included in the scope of the segment. For instance, Mirantis’s OpenStack-based platform for building a 5G edge network infrastructure using network function virtualization (NFV) technologies, as well as Red Hat’s OpenStack Platform deploying on commercially available off-the-shelf (COTS) hardware, have both been included.

7.1.7 Transport operating systems (OS)

This segment considers the total revenue generated through the sales of software (operating system) to provide transport network support connectivity in backhaul, midhaul, and fronthaul networks, as well as the software to deliver network slicing support, switching support, and multilayer-optimized packet and optical transport network support. For instance, Ribbon Communications’ “Muse” software suite, which delivers support for improved automation with software-defined networking (SDN), enhanced multilayer network optimization, and complete life-cycle management, has been considered.

7.1.8 Operations support systems (OSS)

This segment considers the total revenue generated through the sales of network monitoring equipment and software installed for network monitoring, asset monitoring, network configuration, service provisioning, and fault management – for instance, Amdocs’ “NEO suite”, a service and network automation platform that delivers network-as-a-service (NaaS), 5G edge orchestration and slicing.

8 MARKET DEEP-DIVES

8.1 Global perspective

The US, China, and the EU-27 account for over 50 percent of the global 4G / 5G infrastructure market.

The EU market is valued at USD 4.71 bn, smaller than China and the US, which are valued at USD 10.64 bn and 6.17, respectively. Apart from these behemoths, Japan, South Korea and the UK are three of the largest infrastructure markets, and three of the most advanced 5G countries, given the size of their populations. The market in Japan is worth USD 1.83 bn, the UK is worth USD 1.16 bn, and South Korea is slightly smaller at USD 0.95 bn. The spread of spending across RAN, Core, Transport and DC, and OSS is roughly equal across the major geographies, though there are often notable differences between the ratios spent on 4G and 5G within individual domains (Figure 15).

Figure 15: Global 4G / 5G market across geographies³⁸

8.2 EU-27

The EU-27 market Infrastructure market is heavily dominated by Huawei, Ericsson and Nokia. Experts estimate that in 2019, Huawei had 28 percent of Europe's total mobile infrastructure market, with Ericsson on 27 percent and Nokia on 23 percent.³⁹

Within the 4G and 5G RAN infrastructure market specifically, the trend continues, with Huawei leading, Ericsson a close second, and Nokia in third place. ZTE commands less than 10 percent of the RAN market. Their combined RAN market share is roughly 90 percent. Huawei has a particularly strong market position, commanding 32 percent of the antenna systems market segment, and 33 percent of the 4G basebands segment. Huawei's strength in Europe is built on its support for not only 4G and 5G, but also legacy network systems. By providing "single RAN" systems at low prices, Huawei became a crucial vendor in many MNOs' networks during the 4G era. Huawei said in February 2020 that it had signed 91 5G commercial contracts globally, among which more than half had come from Europe.⁴⁰ However, concern over the political uncertainty surrounding Huawei has encouraged some MNOs to decrease their reliance on Huawei in their 5G networks, an effect that has likely been magnified in 2020. By reducing the percentage of the 5G network that uses Huawei equipment, the potential costs related to replacing newly bought Huawei equipment before the end of its lifecycle can be mitigated. This effect can be seen in the spending on 5G basebands (CU/DU) – Huawei received only 24 percent of aggregated EU spending on 5G basebands, compared to 33 percent on 4G basebands, with spending shifting primarily to Ericsson.

³⁸ Arthur D. Little analysis, expert interviews

³⁹ <https://www.lightreading.com/5g/ericsson-huawei-and-nokias-5g-wins-are-no-big-deal/a/d-id/757677>

⁴⁰ <https://www.globaltimes.cn/content/1195119.shtml>

On an aggregated European scale, “new kids” hold a very small percentage of the market (less than 3 percent) and contained within the “others” segment. Though they have larger market shares in some individual European markets, not all markets are experimenting with their equipment, and thus their overall market presence in the EU is limited – for the moment at least.

Figure 16: EU-27 4G and 5G RAN market size and value shares, 2019, USD mn⁴¹

EU core infrastructure spending is still predominately focused on EPC rather than 5G core – 5G core receives only 21 percent of total core spending. This figure is higher for the four major EU markets, at 30, 22, 27 and 24 percent for Germany, France, Italy and Spain, respectively, which showcases their more advanced positions concerning 5G rollouts.

In the core domain, we more clearly see the impact of uncertainty and restrictions around Huawei. Restrictions in EU countries specifically reference the security concerns around Huawei in the core, and the EU Commission recommended “relevant restrictions for suppliers considered to be high risk including necessary exclusions for key assets considered as critical and sensitive (such as the core network functions)”.⁴² As such, Huawei’s market share in 5G core is only 16 percent, down from 26 percent in EPC. Ericsson and Nokia both benefit as a result. Cisco, Juniper and ZTE all maintain small market shares of under 10%.

The numerous small players and “new kids” in the EU-27 Core segment make up 11 percent of the 5GC market. The breakdown can be seen below in Figure 17.

⁴¹ Arthur D. Little analysis, expert interviews

⁴² <https://techcrunch.com/2020/01/29/no-pan-eu-huawei-ban-as-commission-endorses-5g-risk-mitigation-plan/>

4G and 5G Core Infrastructure Market Size and Value Shares

EU-27, 2019, in USD mn

Figure 17: EU-27 4G and 5G core market size and value shares, 2019, USD mn⁴³

In the Net OS/Kubernetes market segment, the EU relies heavily upon Ericsson and Nokia, which command 29 and 24 percent market shares, respectively.

Net OS / Kubernetes and Transport OS Market Size and Value Shares

EU-27, 2019, in USD mn

Figure 18: EU-27 Net OS/Kubernetes and transport market size and value shares, 2019, USD mn⁴⁴

As in Net OS/Kubernetes, in OSS, Ericsson and Nokia command significant market share. Given that the role of an OSS provider is effectively to manage the network, supporting functions such as network configuration and fault management, it is unsurprising that the same vendors would dominate OSS as dominated the rest of the network. At the same time, two other European vendors, Comarch (a Polish vendor) and Altran (a French vendor), which are not visible in OSS systems elsewhere, together maintain 8 percent of the European OSS market, perhaps showing the slight preference of European MNOs for European vendors.

NEC-owned Netcracker also has a strong presence with operators in Europe for OSS, which offers a potential entry point for NEC into the European market. For now, NEC is tight-lipped about its contracts for mobile networks, saying only that it is holding feasibility demonstrations for “a number of customers and we are

⁴³ Arthur D. Little analysis, expert interviews

⁴⁴ Arthur D. Little analysis, expert interviews

engaged in commercial discussions with others,” but it is feasible that it could look to enter the market with a wider range of network components in the near future.

The full breakdown of the EU-27 5G OSS market is given below in Figure 19.

Figure 19: EU-27 operations support systems market size and value shares, 2019, USD mn⁴⁵

8.2.1 Germany

The German government has claimed that although there won't be an outright ban of Huawei gear, its use should be heavily restricted. Yet, Huawei gear is extremely widespread throughout German networks. Strand Consult, an advisory group, estimates that Huawei accounts for 65 percent of Deutsche Telekom's entire RAN, with Ericsson providing the remainder. Meanwhile, around 50 percent of Telefónica's RAN products in Germany are Huawei, and O2 Germany is dependent on Huawei as an equipment provider alongside Nokia.⁴⁶ Unless it wants to leave some 5G "not spots," each of these companies would have to replace all their Huawei gear in the case of a ban. Thus, we already see a decrease in the quantity of equipment purchased from Huawei across 4G and 5G components – in late 2019, Vodafone confirmed that Nokia was replacing Huawei in parts of Vodafone Germany's core network, and Deutsche Telekom was considering increasing its reliance on Ericsson. The full breakdown of the German RAN market can be seen below in Figure 20, and the Core market in Figure 21.

⁴⁵ Arthur D. Little analysis, expert interviews

⁴⁶ 1) <https://www.verdict.co.uk/rollout-5g-germany/>

2) <https://www.lightreading.com/5g/germany-stops-short-of-huawei-ban-but-raises-bar-to-entry/d/d-id/764300>

4G and 5G RAN Infrastructure Market Size and Value Shares

Germany, 2019, in USD mn

Figure 20: Germany 4G and 5G RAN market size and value shares, 2019, USD mn⁴⁷

4G and 5G Core Infrastructure Market Size and Value Shares

Germany, 2019, in USD mn

Figure 21: Germany 4G and 5G core market size and value shares, 2019, USD mn⁴⁸

8.2.2 France

The French authorities have decided to approve the use of Huawei gear but only in non-core parts of the 5G network. Mobile network operators are afraid that despite the decision, France may still restrict the use of Huawei equipment during the rollout of its 5G network. France is likely to abide by directives given by European Union industry chief Thierry Breton, who warned governments against using 5G equipment from risky vendors such as Huawei.⁴⁹ oRANge has already selected Ericsson and Nokia and avoided Huawei altogether. Iliad SA announced a strategic agreement in September 2020 with Nokia for the rollout of 5G networks in France and Italy.⁵⁰ However, the decision to allow Huawei equipment away from the core parts of the network will still affect French operators Bouygues Telecom and Altice Europe's SFR, for which Huawei equipment makes up

⁴⁷ Arthur D. Little analysis, expert interviews

⁴⁸ Arthur D. Little analysis, expert interviews

⁴⁹ <https://www.cpomagazine.com/cyber-security/france-authorizes-the-use-of-huawei-equipment-in-its-5g-network-while-plans-for-a-new-factory-are-underway/>

⁵⁰ <https://www.spglobal.com/marketintelligence/en/news-insights/trending/levfdosvkqxhbf9tnc7kzw2>

close to half of their network infrastructure.⁵¹ The full breakdown of RAN spending is given below in Figure 22, and Core spending in Figure 23.

Figure 22: France 4G and 5G RAN market size and value shares, 2019, USD mn⁵²

Figure 23: France 4G and 5G core market size and value shares, 2019, USD mn⁵³

8.2.3 Italy

As expected, Italian operators primarily stick to Ericsson, Nokia and Huawei as their main RAN vendors. Italian carrier Vodafone announced the launch of commercial 5G services in five cities across the country, using equipment from Nokia and Huawei for the deployment of commercial 5G. Operator Wind Tre chose Ericsson and ZTE, and recently announced the completion of a project to roll out a 5G-ready network

⁵¹ <https://www.cpomagazine.com/cyber-security/france-authorizes-the-use-of-huawei-equipment-in-its-5g-network-while-plans-for-a-new-factory-are-underway/>

⁵² Arthur D. Little analysis, expert interviews

⁵³ Arthur D. Little analysis, expert interviews

throughout Italy, with ZTE having installed some 20,000 5G-ready transmission sites in over 100 provinces all over the country.⁵⁴

Although the Italian government has not yet restricted the use of Huawei in the core, MNOs have still begun to divert funding away from Huawei in the Core domain for 5G – spending on Huawei 5G Core is only 11 percent of total Italian 5GC spending. Despite Italy’s close links with China through initiatives such as China’s Belt and Road Initiative, MNOs are fearful that restrictions might manifest themselves soon. Indeed, an Italian parliamentary body recently told the government to “very seriously” consider restricting Huawei Technologies and other Chinese equipment suppliers, and that concerns about using Chinese companies to install and maintain 5G networks in Italy were “largely grounded”.⁵⁵ In July 2020, Telecom Italia (TIM) excluded Huawei from a tender for the 5G core network it is preparing to build in Italy, instead inviting suppliers Cisco, Ericsson, Nokia, Mavenir, and Affirmed Networks. (ZTE and Samsung were also excluded from the list.)⁵⁶ And operator Wind Tre selected Ericsson to virtualize its core network as part of the evolution of its network to 5G core. The overall breakdown of the Italian RAN market can be seen below in Figure 24, and the core market in Figure 25.

Figure 24: Italy 4G and 5G RAN market size and value shares, 2019, USD mn⁵⁷

⁵⁴ <https://www.telecompaper.com/news/wind-tre-zte-complete-5g-ready-network-project--1320934>

⁵⁵ <https://www.scmp.com/news/world/europe/article/3043061/italian-lawmakers-push-huawei-5g-ban>

⁵⁶ <https://www.insidetelecom.com/italy-decides-to-exclude-huawei-from-5g-core-network-deployment/>

⁵⁷ Arthur D. Little analysis, expert interviews

4G and 5G Core Infrastructure Market Size and Value Shares

Italy, 2019, in USD mn

Figure 25: Italy 4G and 5G core market size and value shares, 2019, USD mn⁵⁸

8.2.4 Spain

In Spain, the government continues to allow the use of Huawei equipment, and thus Spanish MNOs are continuing to invest in Huawei 5G gear almost to the same extent as in 4G Huawei gear. oRANge SA has agreements with Ericsson and Huawei, which continue to manage 60 and 40 percent of the telco's 5G network, respectively; Telefonica has inked its 5G agreements with Ericsson and Nokia; and Vodafone previously said that it was working with Huawei and Ericsson in the deployment of the 5G network. Ericsson is very strong within the Spanish market, with all MNOs relying to some extent on its equipment. Nokia lags behind, in third place. The breakdowns for RAN and Core can be seen below in Figure 26 and Figure 27.

4G and 5G RAN Infrastructure Market Size and Value Shares

Spain, 2019, in USD mn

Figure 26: Spain 4G and 5G RAN market size and value shares, 2019, USD mn⁵⁹

⁵⁸ Arthur D. Little analysis, expert interviews

⁵⁹ Arthur D. Little analysis, expert interviews

4G and 5G Core Infrastructure Market Size and Value Shares

Spain, 2019, in USD mn

Figure 27: Spain 4G and 5G core market size and value shares, 2019, USD mn⁶⁰

8.3 United States of America

The US market for 4G and 5G infrastructure is second only to China in scale.

RAN makes up 60 percent of the total spending within the US 4G-5G infrastructure market. Of note is the relative lack of Chinese vendors in the US RAN market – Huawei only takes 5 percent of the Antenna Systems market share, and ZTE is hardly present in the market at all. Of course, the weakness of Chinese vendors has been exacerbated by US posturing and security concerns, but also reflects longer-term preference in the US for companies to use American or European suppliers instead of Chinese ones. Ericsson and Nokia together command roughly 80 percent of the market.

Meanwhile, new entry Samsung’s market share remained small as of 2019, at 7 percent in Antenna Systems and 10 percent in 5G basebands but has since picked up steam in 2020. In September 2020, Samsung was awarded a USD 6.6 bn contract with Verizon to provide 5G equipment between 2020 and the end of 2025. It represents the attempts at diversification by US MNOs, which are currently stuck with the duopoly of Ericsson and Nokia. Given recent contracts, Samsung RAN market share in 2020 is likely to be significantly higher, with Nokia’s slightly lower.

The US is one of the leading proponents of oRAN, with all leading MNOs looking to find cheaper and “homegrown” alternatives to expensive European options. As such, AltioStar takes a 5 percent cut of total 5G basebands revenue, and Mavenir takes 6 percent. It is one of the few geographies in which we see a “new kid” claiming any market share in Antenna Systems. A full segmentation of the market can be seen below in Figure 28.

⁶⁰ Arthur D. Little analysis, expert interviews

4G and 5G RAN Infrastructure Market Size and Value Shares

United States of America, 2019, in USD mn

Figure 28: US 4G and 5G RAN market size and value shares, 2019, USD mn⁶¹

In the US market, a diverse set of vendors supplies EPC, with no one player taking over 30 percent of the total market share. The US has a relatively high share of 5G core as a percentage of total spending on core, which showcases advanced progress in moving toward a SA network. Verizon plans to deploy a SA core in 2021 and has already announced lab trials. T-Mobile already released its SA core in August 2020.

Ericsson and Nokia are the two leading vendors, together commanding over 50 percent of the 5G core market share. Cisco is comparatively strong compared to its position in other markets, at 15 percent market share. Alongside Nokia, Cisco is the key vendor for T-Mobile’s 5G core platform.

As with RAN components, we see the relative bias toward these “homegrown” US vendors, such as Cisco and Juniper, which command higher market shares in the US than in other markets, as well as “new kid” vendors CommScope and Mavenir. Moreover, there is a notable lack of any Huawei/ZTE market presence in 5G core – which already makes clear the impact of US sanctions and restrictions. The full US Core market can be seen below in Figure 29.

⁶¹ Arthur D. Little analysis, expert interviews

4G and 5G Core Infrastructure Market Size and Value Shares

United States of America, 2019, in USD mn

Figure 29: US 4G and 5G core market size and value shares, 2019, USD mn⁶²

Within the US Net OS / Kubernetes segment, “homegrown” OpenStack software vendors command significant market share. These vendors allow MNOs to build and manage public clouds using open-source software. Mirantis and Red Hat, two of the leading global OpenStack vendors, together take almost 50 percent of the US market revenue. Ericsson and Nokia are relegated to some of the smallest vendors in the market.

The US Transport OS market contains a similar vendor set to those in the core market, with Fujitsu, Cisco and Juniper all making appearances. A full breakdown of both markets is given below in Figure 30.

Net OS / Kubernetes and Transport OS Market Size and Value Shares

United States of America, 2019, in USD mn

Figure 30: US Net OS / Kubernetes and transport market size and value shares, 2019, USD mn⁶³

US 5G operations support systems leading vendors include Amdocs, Ericsson and Netcracker, at 23, 17 and 13 percent market shares, respectively. The full breakdown can be seen below in Figure 31.

⁶² Arthur D. Little analysis, expert interviews

⁶³ Arthur D. Little analysis, expert interviews

Operations Support Systems (OSS) Market Size and Value Shares

United States of America, 2019, in USD mn

Figure 31: US operations support systems market size and value shares, 2019, USD mn

8.4 China

China is by far the largest market globally in terms of infrastructure spending, over double the size of EU market. China spends over USD 10 bn per year – hence why China is so advanced in its 5G rollout plans.

In RAN, we see the relative strength of homegrown RAN vendors Huawei and ZTE, which have long been awarded the bulk of network contracts, leaving a smaller share for Ericsson and Nokia. Huawei and ZTE took the lion’s share of 5G contracts from China Mobile, worth a total of 37.1 billion yuan (USD 5.6 bn), as the carrier looks to accelerate its next-generation mobile network in 2020.⁶⁴ Huawei was awarded 57.2 percent of the contract, followed by ZTE at 28.7 percent and Ericsson at 11.5 percent. Smaller Chinese company CICT was given the remaining 2.2 percent of the carrier’s total 232,143 planned 5G base stations in 2020, which covered 28 provinces. Nokia reportedly bid for but failed to win a contract. Overall, Huawei and ZTE have shouldered most of China’s 5G push for 2020, as they secured most orders to build 5G base stations for China Mobile, China Unicom and China Telecom, the country’s three key carriers. The breakdown of the RAN market is given in Figure 32 below.

4G and 5G RAN Infrastructure Market Size and Value Shares

China, 2019, in USD mn

⁶⁴ <https://www.silicon.co.uk/workspace/huawei-zte-china-mobile-5g-338462>

Figure 32: China 4G and 5G RAN Market Size and Value Shares, 2019, USD mn⁶⁵

The choice of core vendors is largely unsurprising, with Huawei commanding the highest market share and ZTE in second highest. China spends more on 5G core than any other nation in absolute terms, though slightly less as a percentage of total core spending when compared to the US or EU-27. The full breakdown can be seen below in Figure 33.

Figure 33: China 4G and 5G core market size and value shares, 2019, USD mn⁶⁶

Unlike the US, in which new OpenStack vendors have a large market share, the Chinese Net OS / Kubernetes market remains dominated by the large vendors – Huawei, Ericsson, Nokia and ZTE take roughly 65 percent of market revenue. Red Hat and Mirantis combined only take 18 percent of total revenue.

In Transport OS, the big four firms again dominate, with almost 80 percent of market revenue. Juniper, Ribbon and Cisco all take small market shares as well. The breakdown of these two markets is given below in Figure 34.

⁶⁵ Arthur D. Little analysis, expert interviews

⁶⁶ Arthur D. Little analysis, expert interviews

Net OS / Kubernetes and Transport OS Market Size and Value Shares

China, 2019, in USD mn

Figure 34: China Net OS/Kubernetes and transport market size and value shares, 2019, USD mn⁶⁷

Unsurprisingly given the vendor breakdown in the other segments, the market for operations support systems in China is also dominated by Huawei and ZTE, who command 35 and 17 percent market shares, respectively. Given that they supply so many individual components of the network, they are clear choices to provide 5G OSS. The market size and shares can be seen below in Figure 35.

Operations Support Systems (OSS) Market Size and Value Shares

China, 2019, in USD mn

Figure 35: China operations support systems market size and value shares, 2019, USD mn⁶⁸

8.5 United Kingdom

The UK was the first country in Europe to trust in Huawei equipment, with BT signing a deal as far back as 2005 with the Chinese provider, beginning a strong relationship. Alongside Ericsson and Nokia, Huawei was a key vendor for 3G and 4G rollouts across the UK. BT uses Huawei for two-thirds of its 2G and 4G sites, and has been introducing Huawei's 5G tech at these sites too; Vodafone has used the firm for one-third of its 2G, 3G and 4G sites, and is also introducing 5G; Three has been replacing its previous 3G and 4G networks with

⁶⁷ Arthur D. Little analysis, expert interviews

⁶⁸ Arthur D. Little analysis, expert interviews

Huawei technology, with the firm also its “sole 5G supplier”.⁶⁹ Only O2 does not use Huawei within its own networks, although it shares some of its network with Vodafone, so may face issues as it upgrades its technology. However, with the recent government regulations surrounding Huawei, this market share has already begun to decrease. As of 2019, Huawei had gone from a 35 percent share in 4G basebands to a 27 percent share in 5G basebands. In 2020, this trend has likely accelerated with the formal ban of all Huawei network equipment⁷⁰. Ericsson and Nokia gained market share as a result.

As it is one of the most advanced 5G countries in the EU, spending on 5G components is relatively high in the UK. This can be seen in the slightly higher percentage of RAN spending on 5G basebands compared to in other markets, to the benefit of “new kids” such as Parallel Wireless, which notably is the sixth-largest vendor in the UK for this segment. Mavenir, another “new kid”, is the fifth largest. Vodafone UK plans to use both for its ecosystem of oRAN players. The market breakdown for RAN is given below in Figure 36.

Figure 36: UK 4G and 5G RAN market size and value shares, 2019, USD mn⁷¹

Unsurprisingly, the UK also has a disproportionately high level of spending on 5G core as opposed to EPC, with 31 percent of total core spending going toward 5G core. Even in the core, Huawei has a significant market presence, and as of 2019, continued to receive revenue in both EPC and 5GC. Given the restrictions on Huawei equipment in July 2020, this will have changed.

Ericsson and Nokia are unsurprisingly the largest two vendors, and smaller vendors such as Cisco, Samsung and NEC all receive small market shares in 5GC. The full breakdown of UK core vendors can be seen below in Figure 37.

⁶⁹ <https://www.wired.co.uk/article/why-is-uk-banning-huawei-5g>

⁷⁰ <https://www.bbc.com/news/technology-53403793>

⁷¹ Arthur D. Little analysis, expert interviews

4G and 5G Core Infrastructure Market Size and Value Shares

UK, 2019, in USD mn

Figure 37: UK 4G and 5G Core market size and value shares, 2019, USD mn⁷²

8.6 Japan

Japan has been a technological leader in telecoms since the 3G rollouts during the early 2000s. This leadership is shown by its relatively high level of spending on 4G and 5G infrastructure. Since 4G capacities are almost full around the country, Japan is one of the few countries with actual consumer demand for 5G, which has encouraged rollouts and enabled a business case.

Japan historically enjoyed a vibrant set of “homegrown” vendors. Many failed to compete at scale during the 4G era and shrank. However, Japanese vendors NEC and Fujitsu still retain significant market presence in Japan – roughly 10 percent of RAN revenues each. Rakuten, the innovative new entry to the Japanese mobile market, plans to launch both 4G and 5G services using Japanese-made RAN from NEC, rather than relying on Korean gear or alternatives from Huawei. In fact, Japan announced that Huawei was banned from public procurement as of April 2019, and thus Chinese market shares are almost non-existent.

Meanwhile, Japan is at the forefront of oRAN. In February 2020, Rakuten launched the world’s first container-based, cloud-native 5G RAN software, developed in collaboration with AltioStar and Intel. As a result, AltioStar claims 7 percent of the 5G basebands market.

⁷² Arthur D. Little analysis, expert interviews

4G and 5G RAN Infrastructure Market Size and Value Shares

Japan, 2019, in USD mn

Figure 38: Japan 4G and 5G RAN market size and value shares, 2019, USD mn⁷³

As an advanced 5G country, Japan directs a relatively high percentage of core spending toward 5G core. Japanese vendor NEC gained significant market strength during the transition from 4G to 5G, from 8 to 14 percent. The breakdown can be seen below in Figure 39.

4G and 5G Core Infrastructure Market Size and Value Shares

Japan, 2019, in USD mn

Figure 39: Japan 4G and 5G core market size and value shares, 2019, USD mn⁷⁴

8.7 South Korea

Like Japan, South Korea is one of the few countries that can generate consumer demand for 5G, since 4G infrastructure has largely reached its capacity. South Korea also sees 5G to cement the position it has achieved as a powerful global technology player through its leadership in this area. There is no doubt that South Korea is the most advanced in its 5G rollouts of any country.

South Korea's Samsung leads the market in all segments of RAN, most significantly in 5G basebands, for which it achieves 34 percent market share. Chinese vendors have small 4G shares but lose out in 5G.

⁷³ Arthur D. Little analysis, expert interviews

⁷⁴ Arthur D. Little analysis, expert interviews

4G and 5G RAN Infrastructure Market Size and Value Shares

South Korea, 2019, in USD mn

Figure 40: South Korea 4G and 5G RAN market size and value shares, 2019, USD mn⁷⁵

A similar vendor landscape exists in South Korea for core as for RAN. Samsung, Ericsson and Nokia have the largest shares of market revenue. Huawei and ZTE both receive 10 percent or less. South Korea devotes the largest percentage of total core spending toward 5G core of any country in the world – well over 40 percent of all core spending is focussed on 5GC.

A breakdown of the South Korean core market is given below in Figure 41.

4G and 5G Core Infrastructure Market Size and Value Shares

South Korea, 2019, in USD mn

Figure 41: South Korea 4G and 5G core market size and value shares, 2019, USD mn⁷⁶

⁷⁵ Arthur D. Little analysis, expert interviews

⁷⁶ Arthur D. Little analysis, expert interviews

9 HOW WE SEE THE MARKET DEVELOPING

5G deployment is taking place more slowly than expected in Europe. As of Q4 2019, only 1 percent of 4G sites had been upgraded to 5G across the EU-27, compared to 98 percent in South Korea and 7 percent in the US. By 2025, Western European investment in 5G is expected to represent just 9 percent of the global total, compared to South Korea's 7 percent, 23 percent in the US, and China's 45 percent.⁷⁷ There are three main reasons for this.

1. Lack of use-cases in Europe – consumers are not perceived to need faster connection, and Europe still has capacity on its 4G networks. No business use cases have yet been concretely established and MNO rollouts are currently primarily branding opportunities.
2. European MNOs are cash strapped with little money to fund 5G – competition among European vendors is at an all-time high, resulting in low margins and a subsequent lack of cash to spend on investment.
3. Challenging regulation and lack of European initiatives – regulators have been rather slow to auction spectrum and charged high prices; there has not been clarity on the situation with Huawei, which has forced MNOs to delay investment; there is a lack of a common EU initiative to fund projects and encourage common standards and spectrum sharing.

Surprisingly, there is little sign that COVID-19 has delayed rollouts in Europe. Most operators' 5G spending is as predicted from before the crisis – though some smaller operators have been affected – since COVID-19 has had little impact on MNO revenues. Most delays have been the result of a COVID-19-induced decrease in the number of teams available for on-site deployment, as well as disruption to supply chains, rather than MNO CAPEX cuts. Instead, the main impact of COVID-19 has been involved to decreasing consumer confidence around 5G, with rising concerns over radiation, and conspiracies around government plots to use 5G as an excuse for increased surveillance. These theories are easily discredited, and the EU has a role to play in discrediting them to smooth rollouts.

Meanwhile, technological developments in oRAN, virtualization and SDNs are setting the stage to offer a serious challenge to the traditional vendor landscape. By disaggregating software and hardware and agreeing upon universal standards through groups such as the O-RAN Alliance, small players will likely begin to enter the market. The technology is not there yet, but it will come, likely within the next two to five years. When it does, the whole framework of the vendor market is set to change, as smaller players will be able to compete in specific areas without having to offer the full swathe of networking equipment, and thus the market will broaden. Restrictions of Huawei network equipment are only likely to accelerate this shift, as it offers a hedge against a potential duopoly of Ericsson and Nokia in the West.

For Europe, increased global competition, and the broader vendor landscape that comes hand in hand with a shift toward oRAN, represents both a challenge to its vendors and an opportunity for the broader market. On the one hand, it would likely depress vendor profit margins, which are required for investment into R&D. Without them, technological development would slow, and European vendors might lose their current market-leading positions. On the other hand, there is an opportunity for new European players to enter the market. Perhaps more importantly, increased technological innovation is likely to drive down prices for MNOs and enable faster rollouts of 5G in Europe. Europe collectively needs a plan of action to juggle these dual objectives. Without one, Europe's future at the forefront of telecoms could be at stake.

⁷⁷ <https://www.politico.eu/sponsored-content/5g-and-europes-recovery/>

10 APPENDIX – LIMITATIONS TO RESEARCH DESIGN

This analysis covers key geographies mentioned in the research scope. As a result, conclusions about non-key geographies (this includes all markets, which are not explicitly mentioned in the research scope) cannot be drawn in a reliable manner.

Moreover, as 5G is still in its infancy, a lot of uncertainty persists. Therefore, market estimates or projections on future trends are subject to a high degree of volatility. In addition, as the development of 5G networks is still in the nascent stage, lots of trial and error testing is necessary during the implementation process of 5G network infrastructure. Various test and measurement equipment is used during those implementation procedures. Due to its nascent stage, the market for such equipment is also excluded from the research scope.

Another limitation arises when considering the inseparability of 4G and 5G network components. For example, it is not possible to execute a clear cut between network domains, such as “systems” and “core”. This dependability leads to an inevitable overlap. The same holds true for deployment type. Due to overlapping structures, a clear cut between mobile private networks and public networks is not feasible. As a result, the research scope will only refer to public networks as those account for the vast majority in comparison to private networks.

Lastly, hardware components in the network domain “transport” and “data center” are also not part of the research scope. Therefore, fiber cables or servers and their respective vendors will be omitted. Various services, such as data and network managed services and the related infrastructure for those services, which includes optical fiber networks, the system integrator market and the professional services market (provided by telecom operators) are not within the research scope.

11 APPENDIX – SUMMARY TABLES

11.1 Overview 4G and 5G Infrastructure Market

11.1.1 4G and 5G Infrastructure Market by NW Domain and Geography

Selected Key Markets, 2019, in USD mn		USA	China	Japan	South Korea	EU-27	UK
Market Size		6,171	10,638	1,826	945	4,706	1,159
Share of NW domain	Radio Access Network (RAN)	60%	66%	60%	59%	60%	58%
	Core (EPC and 5GC)	17%	21%	20%	17%	19%	16%
	Transport and DC (Transport OS and Net OS/Kubernetes)	8%	5%	8%	9%	7%	9%
	Operational Support Systems (OSS)	14%	8%	13%	15%	14%	17%

11.2 EU-27

11.2.1 4G and 5G RAN Market Size and Value Shares

EU-27, 2019, in USD mn		4G & 5G Antenna Systems	4G Basebands	5G Basebands (CU/DU)
Market Size		1,881	760	161
Market Share	Samsung	-	-	4%
	ZTE	8%	8%	6%
	Nokia	22%	21%	22%
	Ericsson	29%	29%	34%
	Huawei	32%	33%	25%
	Others	9%	9%	9%

11.2.2 4G and 5G Core Infrastructure Market Size and Value Shares

EU-27, 2019, in USD mn		Evolved Packet Core (EPC)	5G Core (5GC)
Market Size		715	192
Market Share	Juniper	6%	-
	Cisco	6%	5%
	ZTE	8%	7%
	Nokia	19%	26%
	Huawei	26%	16%

	Ericsson	27%	34%
	Others	8%	12%

11.2.3 Net OS / Kubernetes and Transport OS Market Size and Value Shares

EU-27, 2019, in USD mn		Net OS / Kubernetes	Transport Operating System (OS)
Market Size		241	89
Market Share	Oracle	3%	-
	Mirantis	4%	-
	Canonical	4%	-
	AWS	5%	-
	Red Hat	5%	-
	Vmware	7%	-
	Google	10%	-
	Ciena	-	5%
	Huawei	-	7%
	ZTE	-	7%
	Infinera	-	9%
	Juniper	-	14%
	Nokia	24%	20%
	Ericsson	29%	24%
Others	9%	14%	

11.2.4 Operations Support Systems (OSS) Market Size and Value Shares

EU-27, 2019, in USD mn		Operations Support Systems (OSS)
Market Size		667
Market Share	Ericsson	27%
	Nokia	22%
	Netcracker	18%
	Amdocs	9%
	ALTRAN	5%
	HPE	4%
	Comarch	3%

	Oracle	3%
	Others	9%

11.3 Germany

11.3.1 4G and 5G RAN Market Size and Value Shares

Germany, 2019, in USD mn		4G & 5G Antenna Systems	4G Basebands	5G Basebands (CU/DU)
Market Size		366	128	53
Market Share	ZTE	6%	5%	5%
	Mavenir	-	-	4%
	Nokia	20%	21%	21%
	Ericsson	30%	30%	33%
	Huawei	37%	36%	28%
	Others	7%	6%	9%

11.3.2 4G and 5G Core Infrastructure Market Size and Value Shares

Germany, 2019, in USD mn		Evolved Packet Core (EPC)	5G Core (5GC)
Market Size		112	49
Market Share	Fujitsu	5%	-
	ZTE	7%	-
	Juniper	9%	-
	NEC	-	4%
	Affirmed	-	4%
	Samsung	-	4%
	Mavenir	-	5%
	Cisco	8%	7%
	Huawei	16%	8%
	Nokia	23%	29%
	Ericsson	25%	31%
	Others	7%	8%

11.4 France

11.4.1 4G and 5G RAN Market Size and Value Shares

France, 2019, in USD mn		4G & 5G Antenna Systems	4G Basebands	5G Basebands (CU/DU)
Market Size		348	124	24
Market Share	ZTE	9%	8%	5%
	NET	-	-	4%
	Mavenir	-	-	4%
	Nokia	25%	27%	28%
	Ericsson	27%	28%	29%
	Huawei	32%	31%	23%
	Others	7%	6%	7%

11.4.2 4G and 5G Core Infrastructure Market Size and Value Shares

France, 2019, in USD mn		Evolved Packet Core (EPC)	5G Core (5GC)
Market Size		113	32
Market Share	Fujitsu	5%	-
	Juniper	8%	-
	Huawei	22%	-
	Mavenir	-	3%
	Hawlett Packard	-	3%
	Affirmed	-	4%
	NEC	-	5%
	Cisco	10%	9%
	Nokia	25%	35%
	Ericsson	24%	30%
Others	6%	11%	

11.5 Italy

11.5.1 4G and 5G RAN Market Size and Value Shares

Italy, 2019, in USD mn		4G & 5G Antenna Systems	4G Basebands	5G Basebands (CU/DU)
Market Size		248	89	26
Market Share	ZTE	11%	12%	10%
	Mavenir	-	-	4%
	Nokia	21%	24%	24%
	Ericsson	29%	27%	32%
	Huawei	29%	30%	23%
	Others	10%	7%	7%

11.5.2 4G and 5G Core Infrastructure Market Size and Value Shares

Italy, 2019, in USD mn		Evolved Packet Core (EPC)	5G Core (5GC)
Market Size		88	32
Market Share	Fujitsu	3%	-
	Juniper	7%	-
	ZTE	9%	-
	Mavenir	-	4%
	Affirmed	-	4%
	Cisco	5%	6%
	Nokia	17%	29%
	Ericsson	27%	40%
	Huawei	27%	11%
	Others	5%	6%

11.6 Spain

11.6.1 4G and 5G RAN Market Size and Value Shares

Spain, 2019, in USD mn		4G & 5G Antenna Systems	4G Basebands	5G Basebands (CU/DU)
Market Size		256	86	18
Market Share	ZTE	6%	6%	4%
	Mavenir	-	-	4%
	Nokia	21%	21%	23%
	Huawei	31%	30%	26%
	Ericsson	37%	35%	35%
	Others	5%	8%	8%

11.6.2 4G and 5G Core Infrastructure Market Size and Value Shares

Spain, 2019, in USD mn		Evolved Packet Core (EPC)	5G Core (5GC)
Market Size		56	18
Market Share	Juniper	6%	-
	Mavenir	-	4%
	ZTE	5%	5%
	Cisco	6%	6%
	Nokia	15%	25%
	Ericsson	31%	34%
	Huawei	29%	18%
	Others	8%	8%

11.7 United States of America (USA)

11.7.1 4G and 5G RAN Market Size and Value Shares

USA, 2019, in USD mn		4G & 5G Antenna Systems	4G Basebands	5G Basebands (CU/DU)
Market Size		2,571	914	246
Market Share	Altiostar	4%	4%	4%
	Mavenir	-	-	4%
	Ceragon	4%	-	-
	Huawei	4%	5%	-
	Samsung	7%	7%	10%
	Nokia	34%	35%	32%
	Ericsson	44%	43%	46%
	Others	3%	6%	4%

11.7.2 4G and 5G Core Infrastructure Market Size and Value Shares

USA, 2019, in USD mn		Evolved Packet Core (EPC)	5G Core (5GC)
Market Size		842	218
Market Share	Airspan	4%	-
	Fujitsu	4%	-
	Huawei	5%	-
	Juniper	10%	-
	Hawlett Packard	-	3%
	Mavenir	-	3%
	Commscope	-	3%
	NEC	-	3%
	Samsung	5%	8%
	Cisco	13%	11%
	Ericsson	26%	33%
	Nokia	29%	30%
	Others	4%	6%

11.7.3 Net OS / Kubernetes and Transport OS Market Size and Value Shares

USA, 2019, in USD mn	Net OS / Kubernetes	Transport Operating System (OS)
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Market Size		366	137
Market Share	Metaswitch	4%	-
	Canonical	5%	-
	Oracle	6%	-
	AWS	7%	-
	Vmware	11%	-
	Red Hat	22%	-
	Mirantis	28%	-
	Cisco	-	13%
	Juniper	-	9%
	Fujitsu	-	8%
	Infinera	-	7%
	Ribbon	-	7%
	Ciena	-	6%
	Arista Networks	-	4%
	Aviat Networks	-	4%
	Ericsson	3%	19%
	Nokia	4%	15%
Others	10%	8%	

11.7.4 Operations Support Systems (OSS) Market Size and Value Shares

USA, 2019, in USD mn		Operations Support Systems (OSS)
Market Size		878
Market Share	Amdocs	23%
	Ericsson	17%
	Netcracker	13%
	Oracle	11%
	Nokia	10%
	HPE	6%
	CSG	4%
	Others	16%

11.8 China

11.8.1 4G and 5G RAN Market Size and Value Shares

China, 2019, in USD mn	4G & 5G Antenna Systems	4G Basebands	5G Basebands (CU/DU)
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Market Size		4,555	2,196	284
Market Share	Ericsson	9%	10%	9%
	Nokia	10%	11%	8%
	ZTE	21%	20%	21%
	Huawei	52%	52%	55%
	Others	8%	7%	7%

11.8.2 4G and 5G Core Infrastructure Market Size and Value Shares

China, 2019, in USD mn		Evolved Packet Core (EPC)	5G Core (5GC)
Market Size		1,891	394
Market Share	Fujitsu	4%	-
	Juniper	7%	-
	NEC	-	4%
	Samsung	-	5%
	Cisco	5%	5%
	Ericsson	11%	8%
	Nokia	12%	9%
	ZTE	17%	20%
	Huawei	39%	42%
	Others	5%	7%

11.8.3 Net OS / Kubernetes and Transport OS Market Size and Value Shares

China, 2019, in USD mn		Net OS / Kubernetes	Transport Operating System (OS)
Market Size		379	131
Market Share	Vmware	3%	-
	Matswitch	3%	-
	Radisys	4%	-
	Mirantis	8%	-
	Red Hat	10%	-
	Ribbon	-	3%
	Juniper	-	3%
	Infinera	-	4%
	Cisco	-	6%
	Nokia	11%	10%

	ZTE	12%	24%
	Ericsson	12%	14%
	Huawei	27%	29%
	Others	10%	7%

11.8.4 Operations Support Systems (OSS) Market Size and Value Shares

China, 2019, in USD mn		Operations Support Systems (OSS)
Market Size		667
Market Share	Huawei	35%
	ZTE	17%
	Ericsson	15%
	Nokia	8%
	AsialInfo	6%
	Netcracker	3%
	Others	16%

11.9 United Kingdom UK)

11.9.1 4G and 5G RAN Market Size and Value Shares

UK, 2019, in USD mn		4G & 5G Antenna Systems	4G Basebands	5G Basebands (CU/DU)
Market Size		457	165	53
Market Share	Samsung	6%	5%	6%
	ZTE	9%	8%	-
	NEC	-	-	4%
	Parallel	-	-	4%
	Mavenir	-	-	5%
	Nokia	19%	18%	20%
	Ericsson	26%	26%	25%
	Huawei	33%	35%	27%
	Others	7%	8%	9%

11.9.2 4G and 5G Core Infrastructure Market Size and Value Shares

UK, 2019, in USD mn		Evolved Packet Core (EPC)	5G Core (5GC)
Market Size		127	56
Market Share	ZTE	6%	-
	Juniper	7%	-
	Mavenir	-	4%
	NEC	-	4%
	Parallel	-	4%
	Samsung	-	6%
	Cisco	6%	8%
	Nokia	22%	21%
	Ericsson	24%	28%
	Huawei	26%	20%
	Others	9%	5%

11.10 Japan

11.10.1 4G and 5G RAN Market Size and Value Shares

Japan, 2019, in USD mn		4G & 5G Antenna Systems	4G Basebands	5G Basebands (CU/DU)
Market Size		817	219	60
Market Share	Huawei	4%	4%	-
	Mavenir	-	-	3%
	Altiosstar	5%	4%	7%
	NEC	9%	9%	11%
	Fujitsu	9%	9%	9%
	Samsung	10%	10%	15%
	Ericsson	27%	27%	24%
	Nokia	30%	31%	26%
	Others	6%	6%	5%

11.10.2 4G and 5G Core Infrastructure Market Size and Value Shares

Japan, 2019, in USD mn		Evolved Packet Core (EPC)	5G Core (5GC)
Market Size		223	134
Market Share	Fujitsu	4%	-
	Juniper	7%	-
	Mavenir	-	4%
	Cisco	7%	9%
	NEC	8%	14%
	Samsung	9%	12%
	Ericsson	27%	26%
	Nokia	28%	28%
	Others	10%	7%

11.11 South Korea

11.11.1 4G and 5G RAN Market Size and Value Shares

South Korea, 2019, in USD mn		4G & 5G Antenna Systems	4G Basebands	5G Basebands (CU/DU)
Market Size		397	96	64
Market Share	Fujitsu	3%	-	-
	Altiosstar	-	-	3%
	Mavenir	-	-	5%
	NEC	3%	-	4%
	ZTE	4%	6%	-
	Huawei	11%	11%	8%
	Ericsson	22%	22%	19%
	Nokia	24%	25%	23%
	Samsung	29%	26%	34%
	Others	4%	10%	4%

11.11.2 4G and 5G Core Infrastructure Market Size and Value Shares

South Korea, 2019, in USD mn		Evolved Packet Core (EPC)	5G Core (5GC)
Market Size		96	69
Market Share	ZTE	5%	5%
	Cisco	8%	9%
	Fujitsu	8%	-
	Huawei	10%	8%
	Juniper	11%	-
	Nokia	16%	21%
	Ericsson	16%	19%
	Samsung	18%	29%
	Others	8%	9%